

ME'MORCHILIK

VA QURILISH

MUAMMOLARI

ISSN: 2091-5004

ILMIY TEXNIK JURNAL

27.04.2023

№ MAHSUS SON

PROBLEMS OF ARCHITECTURE AND CONSTRUCTION

(Scientific and technical journal) 27.04.2023 № SPECIAL ISSUE

ПРОБЛЕМЫ АРХИТЕКТУРЫ И СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВА

(научно-технический журнал) 27.04.2023 № СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ ВЫПУСК

Jurnal OAK Hay'atining qaroriga binoan texnika (qurilish, mexanika va mashinasozlik sohalari) fanlari hamda me'morchilik bo'yicha ilmiy maqolalar chop etilishi lozim bo'lgan ilmiy jurnallar ro'yxatiga kiritilgan (guvohnoma №00757. 2000.31.01)

Jurnalimizdagi ingliz tilida chop etilgan maqolalar OAK Rayosatining 2020 yil 30 iyuldagi 283/7.1-son qaroriga asosan xorijiy ilmiy nashrlarda chop etilgan ilmiy maqolalarga tenglashtirilganini ma'lum qiladi.

2023

Google Scholar provides a simple way to broadly search for scholarly literature.

Any status is accepted, from any stage of the research lifecycle

Wikipedia is a free online encyclopedia created by volunteers around the world

Open Journal Systems (OJS) is an open source solution to managing and publishing scholarly journals online.

International Standard Serial Number International centre

UTC 711.4 (075.8)

IMPROVEMENT OF NEIGHBORHOOD CENTERS IN THE RESTORATION OF HISTORIC CITIES

Madiev Farrukh Muysinovich¹, Saidova Navruza¹, Berdikulov Azamat, teachers,

¹Samarkand State University of architecture and construction,
E-mail: djmfarruh@gmail.com +998996222453

Annotation: served as the basis of a holistic generalized scientific model presented in the research of the Neighborhood Center. Its production has become important in the study and development of the ancient manic traditions of the formation of Neighborhood Centers. The existing multi-year history in the historical part of the city of Samarkand, the presence of historical neighborhood centers based on national traditions and defects in the area of infection, restoration and construction of the Universal environment quickly require a professional approach to this area. The first step can be achieved by continuing work on the construction of neighborhood centers as an experiment on the basis of the presented model, and then by practical implementation on the basis of Uzbekistan to create modern neighborhood centers that have been formed for many centuries and serve the rapid development of national traditions.

Keywords: neighborhood, Urban Planning, Samarkand, Center.

Introduction

The study of the development paths of Neighborhood Centers, their compositional-architectural qualities and other architectural features in the urban planning system of cities leads to the conclusion that the objects under study are not only unique objects in Oriental architecture, they are also of great importance in modern urban planning practice.

Alas, the principle of "valuable value" was lost only in the historically formed Urban Planning at that time. In other words, the historically formed system of development of Neighborhood Centers has been disrupted in many places. In the copy plan, an anic system problem occurs in the location of objects. This is explained by the deformation in the urban environment-planning structure in the process of building residential buildings. It gives the assumption that the scale of such changes was even greater because part of the machites had disappeared. The loss of irrigation systems has resulted in the depletion of water reserves in

historic areas resulting in the deterioration of the improvement system. In a word, the building-ruin, which has become an unsuitable place for use [8].

Main part

At present, only some of the buildings have been preserved within the center, while the neighborhood centers have been preserved. They arrived not only in the form of architectural monuments, but also as a center where members of the neighborhood gather and relax. Neighborhood centers today have become tea houses and other general-household and administrative-economic institutions.

Yomini Neighborhood Center on Chiragchi Street, Samarkand City. The Machit building is in a half-ruin State. In order to prevent it from becoming completely destroyed, it is necessary to urgently carry out restoration work. The wooden part of the ensemble is not used. An unplanned Neighborhood Club building was built next to it. Machit walls have large crevices and a

spherical dome is held by a brood. The position of the dome is bloodless, needs reinforcement. In general, the complex is in the state of technical avria. The pool was buried, the tower was not preserved. The loss rate of the initial state is 70 %.

The city of Samarkand is called Abruksim Huja (late XIX century) machiti on Saron Street. Since the founding of the complex, repairs have been carried out once in 1945. Mahalla the elders said that before the repair, a bakery was located in Machit, as a result of which the central column was almost burnt. A cell stands in the south-west corner of Machit. The first case was almost infected. Only the arches have been preserved on the way to the entrance. The porthole is broken, it is located slightly off the Machit, closed by a dome, inside which a pond with water was found. Those who came to prayer around the pool were settled and carried out ablution before the nomosis. On the other side of the wordangaran Kucha there is a pond and a teahouse. The pool was built in one mandate by the time of the Machit formation. Now at the moment it is full of waste. The rate of transmission of the initial state is 60% [6].

The main requirements for the architectural and spatial composition of the neighborhood centers and the formation of the microclimate, the proposal for the reconstruction of the historical neighborhood centers, the result of the method of systematization of solar protection were calculated. Therefore, it is recommended to place neighborhood centers in a closed environment in a part of the city where there is a lot of sunlight. In this case, neighborhood centers are added independently of the street or Square; neighborhood centers with semi-closed environments are placed at the intersection of the streets, taking into account the density and heat level; neighborhood centers with open environments are used in densely populated areas of buildings. In these cases, the

Neighborhood Center is placed at the extension or beginning of the street [9].

From such a point of view, the effective use of elements and the chemo of sunlight are directly proportional to the outdoor environment of the neighborhood centers. In other words, while the expansion of the open environment in neighborhood centers increases the efficiency of microclimate organization tools, the reduction of the open environment, on the contrary, reduces the effectiveness of these tools.

The next requirement for the formation of the structure of the Neighborhood Center is the Coordination of its architectural composition. This is directly related to the formation of the hajm-planned environment of the object.

The practical-planned solution of the Neighborhood Center dictates the use of the principles of spatial composition of the spatial-compositional qualities of the architectural-planned (closed, semi – open and open) species identified in the scientific study, the quality of the continuation of the “simple” and “complex” - historical traditions. This is used depending on whether each of them meets the requirements of one or another type of Neighborhood Centers. The "simple" principle embodies the grouping of structures around the main single-plan environment, which reflects public pedestrian lanes. On the basis of such a principle, closed or Peninsular neighborhood centers can be organized. The "complex" principle groups structures in two or more environments for open-type neighborhood centers, and separate public pedestrian lanes are organized each. In such cases, public pedestrian gutters are often interconnected by greenery elements and juicy decorative equipment. In this case, the architectural-compositional solution should serve to show these elements. The principles of using the environment of residential buildings are also included in the solution of architectural composition issues [10].

16. F.M.Madiev., G'.B.Boboiev, A. Xudoyberdiev; „Yo'llar estetikasining rivojlanishi,"Ta'lim, fan va ishlab chiqarish integratsiyasida intellektual salohiyatli yoshlar – mamlakat taraqqiyotning muhim omili” mavzusidagi XIII respublika ilmiy – amaliy konferensiyasi materaillari",1,2,216-217,2017,

17. F.M.Madiev., G'.B.Boboiev, A. Xudoyberdiev.; „Yo'l-transport hodisalarini tahlil qilishning asosiy vazifalari va usullari.,Arxitektura – qurilish fani va davr respublika ilmiy – amaliy anjumani materaillari.,1,1,224,2017,

18. F.M.Madiev., A. Xudoyberdiev, I.T. Abdiev.; „Avtomobil yo'llarida transport vositasining harakat traektoriyasini to'g'irlash uchun to'siqlar loyixalash va o'rnatish,Shahar qurilishi va xo'jaligining dolzarb masalalarisha bag'ishlangan II respublika ilmiy – texnik anjumi to'plami,1,1,162-163,2017,

19. F.M.Madiev., A. Xudoyberdiev, magistr Q.O'.Saburov; „Shahar ko'chalarida avtomobil yo'llarini yoritish,Shahar qurilishi va xo'jaligining dolzarb masalalarisha bag'ishlangan II respublika ilmiy – texnik anjumi to'plami,1,1,168,2017,

20. F.M.Madiev., M. Xaydavolov, S.U. Rahmonqulov.; „O'zbekistonda XX asr mobaynida urbanizatsiyalashuv jarayoni,Shahar qurilishi va xo'jaligining dolzarb masalalarisha bag'ishlangan II respublika ilmiy – texnik anjumi to'plami,1,1,76-77,2017,

21. F.M.Madiev., A.A.Berdiqulov, D.Ulashov.; „Cutkaning qorong'i davrida avtomobillarning harakatlanish sharoitlari,"Ta'lim, fan va ishlab chiqarish integratsiyasida intellektual salohiyatli yoshlar – mamlakat taraqqiyotning muhim omili” mavzusidagi XIII respublika ilmiy – amaliy konferensiyasi materaillari",1,6,244-247,2018,

17.	U.R.Oktyabirov, SHAHARSOZLIKNI REJALASHTIRISH DARAJALARINING URBANIZATSIYA JARAYONLARIGA TA’SIRI	76--78
18.	Usmonov Erkin Toyirovich, SHAHAR HUDUDLARI QIG’OQLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNINIG ZAMONAVIY PRINSPLARI	79-82
19.	Xatamova Durдона Madaminovna, AXSIKENT QADIMIY HAMMOMLARI ARXITEKTURASI	83--86
20.	<i>Elmurod Haydarov Ashirovich,</i> TURARJOY BINOLARINING VENTILYATSIYA TIZIMLARINI LOYIHALASHDA ZAMONAVIY KOMPYUTER GRAFIK DASTURLARIDAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI	87-89
21.	Azimova Dilrabo Akbarovna, Bobomurodova Mashhura Azimovna , XORIJIY TAJRIBALARIGA ASOSAN LANDSHAFT MUHITI BILAN ZAMONAVIY DIZAYN VA QURILISH TALABLARIGA JAVOB BERADIGAN MUASSASALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH OMILLARINI TAHLIL QILISH	90-95
22.	Nurmuradova Yulduz Bazarovna, Omonovqulov Farruh Farxod o’g’li, SHAHAR SOHASIDAGI MODERNIZATSION MAZMUNNI REJALASHTIRISH.	96-99
23.	Шукуров И.С. ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ БЛАГОУСТРОЙСТВА ТЕРРИТОРИЙ ЖИЛОЙ ЗАСТРОЙКИ КАРАСУВ В ПРИБРЕЖНОЙ ЗОНЕ ЗАРАФШАН	100-104
24.	<i>Fayzulla Ziyatovich Chorshanbayev, Chinnigul Otaqulovna Meliyeva, Boynazarov Mexroj,</i> SHAHAR MUXANDISLIK TARMOQLARINI LOYIHALASH TAKLIFI.	105-110
25.	Элмуратов Баходир Эргашович, Хайдаров Шохбозжон Зухриддин угли, РАСЧИСТКА И ПЛАНИРОВКА ТЕРРИТОРИИ	111-114
26.	Abduraimov Sherzod Muratkulovich, O’RTA OSIYO SHAHARLARINING KELIB CHIQISH GENEZISI	115-117
27.	<i>F.Z. Chorshanbayev, A.F. Ziyatova magistr, A. Rozimov talaba.,</i> TURARJOY BINOLARIDA XONANING ARXITEKTURASINI SAKLLANTIRISH TAMOYILLARI	118-121
28.	<i>Soriev Xolmurod Yaxshimurodovich, Axmedov Baxtiyor Shodiyorovich,</i> V-IX ASRLARDA SO’G’D SHAHARLARI VA ULARDAGI IJTIMOYIY MUNOSABATLAR MASALASI BO’YICHA BA’ZI MA’LUMOTLAR (PANJIKENT SHAHRI MISOLIDA).	122-125
29.	Hasanov Azamat Ozatovich, Sharipov Fozil Odilovich, ADAPTATION OF CONVERTING INDUSTRIAL FACILITIES INTO PUBLIC FUNCTIONAL BUILDINGS	126-130
30.	<i>Madiev Farrukh Muysinovich,</i> Saidova Navruza, Berdikulov Azamat,	131-134
31.	Hasanov Azamat Ozadovich, Matjanov Orazmed Kamiljnovich, ILMIY TADQIQOT VA INNOVATSION MARKAZLARNI ARXITEKTURASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARNI TAHLIL QILISH	135-138
32.	<i>Madiev Farrukh Muysinovich,</i> RESTORATION OF HISTORIC CITIES	139-142
33.	Tursunova Dilnoza Raufjonovna. MARG’ILONNING QADIMGI MAHALLALARI	143-145
34.	Сереева Гулжазира Адилбаевна, ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ ЛОКАЛЬНЫХ СИСТЕМ РАЗМЕЩЕНИЯ ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫХ ЦЕНТРОВ В СЕЛЬСКИХ НАСЕЛЕННЫХ МЕСТ	146-150
35.	Балгаев А.Б. Балгаева Ш.А. Бердиев М. Тошкуллов Ш.Б. ПОНИМАНИЕ ГРАДОСТРОИТЕЛЬНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ В ГЕРМАНИИ	151-156